

D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.1

Protocol for Wild Animals Feces collection and Laboratory Operating Procedure (LOP)

[Compartment 11]

**Version 1
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Protocol for Wild Animal Feces collection and Laboratory Operating Procedure (LOP)

A. Description

Compilation the sampling of Wild Animal feces and points, and further laboratory analysis, ensuring harmonization of testing procedures, which will enhance comparability of the results obtained from different regions of Europe. This protocol will allow answering to different questions from the FED-AMR project.

B. Equipment and material

- Sterile propylene flasks, 50ml
- Sterile plastic bags
- Sterile disposable wooden spatula
- Scale
- Sterile cryotubes

C. Procedure

1. Sampling, transportation and conservation

- Consent for fecal sample collection is given by the farmer/HOAL
- All procedures involving animals are performed in accordance with the European regulations regarding the protection of animals used for experimental and other scientific purposes.
- A pool of 300 g of freshly fecal samples **by animal species**, is collected each at **10 time points** (through 1 year; Table 1: Project Timeline sheet), in each of four HOALs (in different countries: Austria, Portugal and Czech Republic), as well as Ireland and Norway.
- Aseptically collect the targeted **animal species** faecal samples.
- In this case, fecal samples can be collected **from the rectum/cloaca, or from the ground**; if material is collected from the ground it should be from the top of a freshly passed deposit, avoiding deposit areas in contact with the ground.
- Collected samples are introduced into a plastic bag or a screw cap container that is airtight, watertight, and suitably robust (e.g. several 50 ml sterile propylene flasks to achieve the 300 g of feces). [however, **use always** an equal amount of each of the samples in the pool from each specie].

- Subsequently, double-packaging within sealed plastic bags prevent leakage and some cross-contamination of samples and associated packaging materials. [Note: Feces contained only in rectal exam gloves, plastic bags, or rubber-stoppered tubes are unsuitable as they are very frequently comprised by bacterial growth with gas production that can rupture plastic bags, displace stoppers, and allow leakage of the specimen].
- All containers must be clearly and completely labelled (see the coding system at the FED-AMR homepage, and as circulated in Excel file (Timeline_Sample_02_03_2020).
- Conserve immediately samples of each pool at **0°C to 5°C** (DO NOT FREEZE FECAL SAMPLES).
- Samples should be processed at the laboratory within 18 hours (for each pool, so sampling was performed maximum in the day before).
- For wild animals from each pool, performed always by specie, GPS positions of each faecal sample composing the pool are kept in a “Record sheet” during the sampling and further in the database; from the GPS positions, a series of exposure characteristics and variables records for all sampling sites (e.g. soil description, and use type, GPS coordinates, temperature, humidity) may be calculated.

2. Sampling processing

We have 10 individual tubes with 300 g of pooled feces each. Each pool is collected in one of the ten time-points and it contains feces from 3 to 10 animals.

- Pool samples, from each time points, should be very well mixed by stirring thoroughly with a sterile disposable wooden spatula, or other sterile device, for 1-2 minutes.
- From these pools, distribute samples as follows (see Figure 1):
 - weight about 17.5 g of each pool in 10 cryotubes (to store at -80°C as a backup, being sure that it should only be used as last resort, because eDNA will be considerably changed in this frozen sample, and bacteriology results will be also changed);
 - weight 2.75 g from each animal pool, to be used in DNA extraction (2.5 g for eDNA and 0.25 g for total DNA) for qPCR and 2.75 g in triplicate, to be used in DNA extraction for metagenomics (WP2);
 - weight 0.5 g from each animal pool for WP2 (cultivation bacteria in nutrient and minimal media; identification of *Salmonella* spp, and *Escherichia coli*; MICs; WGS from selected bacteria);
 - weight 1 g from each animal pool for WP3 (identification of *Clostridium difficile*; MICs; WGS from selected bacteria);
 - weight 40 g from each animal pool, to be used in quantification (WP4.4);
 - weight 230 g from each animal pool, to be used in quantification (WP4.7).

Tubes should be labelled according to the FED-AMR coding system, to be easy to identify the sample. See information about this coding system at the FED-AMR homepage.

Fig 1. Wild Animals feces sampling at each of the 10 time points (composite sample) to be performed by Austria, Portugal, Czech Republic, as well as Ireland and Norway.

3. For the representativeness of sample

It is very important:

- to **use always** an equal amount of each of the fresh samples for each pools;
- to be sure that a scale with at least two decimal-points are used, to ensure correct weighing of the required amounts;
- to **mix very well** the pooled sample, before using it for DNA extraction (WP2), or bacteriology (WP2, WP3), or quantification (WP4).

4. Conservation in the laboratory and transport to other European regions

- for Bacteriology procedures (WP2., WP3): conserve samples at 0°C to 5°C until bacteriology be processed, which must be with fresh pooled samples [cultivable bacteria and MICs to be performed in each country];
- for Genomics (WP2): conserve samples at 0°C to 5°C until extraction of DNA; DNA extraction must be processed within the next 18h due to eDNA [using harmonized protocol; to be performed in each country];
- if any country cannot perform qPCR, WGS, and metagenomics in the respective lab, DNA should be shipped at -80°C to the receptor lab;
- for quantification in WP4.4.: feces pool is transported frozen, in 200ml dark PP or PET bottles;
- for quantification in WP4.7.: feces pool is transported frozen, in PET bottles.

5. Sample references for wild animal samples

Austria:

Sample Reference	Description	Schedule Month
AT20-Ww1	Austria, wild animals, sample 1	Anytime within one year
AT20-Ww2	Austria, wild animals, sample 2	Anytime within one year
AT20-Ww3	Austria, wild animals, sample 3	Anytime within one year
AT20-Ww4	Austria, wild animals, sample 4	Anytime within one year
AT20-Ww5	Austria, wild animals, sample 5	Anytime within one year
AT20-Ww6	Austria, wild animals, sample 6	Anytime within one year
AT21-Ww7	Austria, wild animals, sample 7	Anytime within one year
AT21-Ww8	Austria, wild animals, sample 8	Anytime within one year
AT21-Ww9	Austria, wild animals, sample 9	Anytime within one year
AT21-Ww10	Austria, wild animals, sample 10	Anytime within one year

Ireland:

Sample Reference	Description	Schedule Month
IE20-Ww1	Ireland, wild animals, sample 1	Anytime within one year
IE20-Ww2	Ireland, wild animals, sample 2	Anytime within one year
IE20-Ww3	Ireland, wild animals, sample 3	Anytime within one year
IE20-Ww4	Ireland, wild animals, sample 4	Anytime within one year
IE20-Ww5	Ireland, wild animals, sample 5	Anytime within one year
IE20-Ww6	Ireland, wild animals, sample 6	Anytime within one year
IE21-Ww7	Ireland, wild animals, sample 7	Anytime within one year
IE21-Ww8	Ireland, wild animals, sample 8	Anytime within one year
IE21-Ww9	Ireland, wild animals, sample 9	Anytime within one year
IE21-Ww10	Ireland, wild animals, sample 10	Anytime within one year

Norway:

Sample Reference	Description	Schedule Month
NO20-Ww1	Norway, wild animals, sample 1	Anytime within one year
NO20-Ww2	Norway, wild animals, sample 2	Anytime within one year
NO20-Ww3	Norway, wild animals, sample 3	Anytime within one year
NO20-Ww4	Norway, wild animals, sample 4	Anytime within one year
NO20-Ww5	Norway, wild animals, sample 5	Anytime within one year
NO20-Ww6	Norway, wild animals, sample 6	Anytime within one year
NO21-Ww7	Norway, wild animals, sample 7	Anytime within one year
NO21-Ww8	Norway, wild animals, sample 8	Anytime within one year
NO21-Ww9	Norway, wild animals, sample 9	Anytime within one year
NO21-Ww10	Norway, wild animals, sample 10	Anytime within one year

Portugal:

Sample Reference	Description	Schedule Month
PT20-Ww1	Portugal, wild animals, sample 1	Anytime within one year
PT20-Ww2	Portugal, wild animals, sample 2	Anytime within one year
PT20-Ww3	Portugal, wild animals, sample 3	Anytime within one year
PT20-Ww4	Portugal, wild animals, sample 4	Anytime within one year
PT20-Ww5	Portugal, wild animals, sample 5	Anytime within one year
PT20-Ww6	Portugal, wild animals, sample 6	Anytime within one year
PT21-Ww7	Portugal, wild animals, sample 7	Anytime within one year
PT21-Ww8	Portugal, wild animals, sample 8	Anytime within one year
PT21-Ww9	Portugal, wild animals, sample 9	Anytime within one year
PT21-Ww10	Portugal, wild animals, sample 10	Anytime within one year

D. References

- EFFORT protocols (e.g. D2.1., D.1.5.)
- General Collection and Handling of Fecal Samples. University of Prince Edward Island (UPEI).
- OIE Terrestrial Manual 2018, Sampling methods (Chapter I.1.1, page 1-11)
- OIE Terrestrial Manual 2018, Collection, submission and storage of diagnostic specimens (Chapter 1.1.2., page 11-22)
- Metzler-Zebeli BU, Lawlor PG, Magowan E, Zebeli Q. 2016. Animals (Basel), 6(3). pii: E18. doi: 10.3390/ani6030018.